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DEVELOPING FLEXIBLE MINDS : EXPLORING BRAIN GYMNASTICS AND NEUROPLASTICITY IN EDUCATION

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ABSTRACT

This poster aims to socialize a course that was offered online and free of charge to educators affiliated with the Association of Teaching Professionals of the Municipality of Mauá/SP (APROMAM), taught by the author, held in April 2024, on “Brain Gymnastics (Neurobics) and Neuroplasticity”. It was developed in three meetings, using theoretical contributions and practical activities, aiming to strengthen memory, increase concentration, stimulate creativity, improve reasoning, reduce stress, maintain brain health, self-knowledge and promote neuroplasticity of its participants.